

DEVELOP SUCCESSFUL VOCABULARY LEARNING STRATEGIES

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Abstract: This article is about choosing appropriate learning strategies while learning new vocabulary in their classrooms.

Key words: vocabulary, word, strategy, goal, cards, puzzle.

English, as an international language, plays an increasingly crucial role in daily life in Uzbekistan. With the increasing of economy and culture between countries, the importance of English is recognized by more and more Uzbek people. In addition to this, it would be better to mention the decision of the Head of State, which was directed to learn foreign languages, especially English, and to develop teaching system. The main purpose of the decision was to teach foreign languages from the nursery schools. More things have changed after the decree, notably the government paid attention to the importance of foreign languages among the young learners that gives opportunity to show our ability of learning international.

Vocabulary plays an important role in English language acquisition, especially for young learners. In the process of vocabulary learning, it is essential not only to know the meaning of particular word, but all the aspects of the word. As for me, while learning a word, sometimes I find it hard to choose a word and when I want to express meaning, I may have some difficulties in selecting a suitable word. Therefore, knowing the organization of the mental lexicon is a good way for EFL learners to acquire vocabulary more successfully.

Understanding the nature of vocabulary is important to the process of selecting appropriate instructional strategies that enable students to master the vocabulary need to learn to read and to read to learn.

In the English classrooms, the teacher teaches students with the same teaching method. However, some students can acquire the language successfully, while others fail. Why does this happen? It may have something to do with some learning strategies. The same learning strategies may be useful for some students but useless for others. It means that, the learners should master some learning strategies to make their language learning more effective. In addition, many studies also show that apart from teaching methodologies, learner strategies are another essential factor that can affect foreign language acquisition. They can help learners become more effective.

Schmitt (1977)[1] provides a useful overview of the rise in importance of strategy use in second language learning, noting that it grew out of an interest in the learner's active role in the learning process. There are numerous strategies we not only need to know, but also we need to master them.

Many researchers give their opinions about vocabulary learning strategies. For instance, Nation develops a general classification of vocabulary learning strategies (Nation 2000: 218-222) [2]. From his beliefs, the first one is planning vocabulary learning, to choose words. Learners should know what their vocabulary goals are; and choose what vocabulary to focus on in items of their selected goals. What is more, learners should also have a clear strategy for deciding what vocabulary to focus on, and where to find this vocabulary. Using various strategies can make the learning process more efficient.

The second vocabulary learning strategy is choosing appropriate sources. In order to cope with new vocabulary when it occurs and to learn unfamiliar vocabulary, learners have to be able to get information about the words. Analyzing word parts is a useful strategy, because being familiar with the stems and affixes can provide useful for seeing connections between related words, checking guesses from context, strengthening form and meaning connections, and in some cases working out the meaning of a word.

There are some vocabulary activities to run in the ESL or EFL classroom. From this point, I want to open four activities that helped me to increase my vocabulary range. I am going to give learners some tips that focus their attention on the vocabulary, require learners to get back the forms and meanings of the new words, and encourage learners to identify and develop a personalized repertory of specific preferred strategies for vocabulary learning.

Activity 1. Keeping a running list of words.

Students usually remember a certain percentage of what they see, and a certain amount of what they hear, but they will remember even more of what they see and hear. In addition, as from my experience, writing a list as keeping a vocabulary notebook is one of many good vocabulary-learning strategies. Keeping a vocabulary list is a good first step, but sometimes it would be boring to learn them in one way. In that case, using unique action such as, drawing the word, making a story about it, or spelling it backwards could be included.

Activity 2. Vocabulary cards.

A very simple yet effective practice activity uses vocabulary cards that contain one question each. As a self-study learner we can use while learning new words. Each card contains only one exercise. Write a question in large enough

print or front in the sheet of paper. Alternatively, we can add multiple choice for these questions. For example,

Multiple-choice exercise: The area between two mountains is called a

_____.

- a. Voucher
- b. Valley
- c. Wound
- d. Wave

Activity 3. Ranking vocabulary items.

In a ranking activity, it is better to rank items according to some factor. For instance, if we are going to learn cities we rank them according to population, or historical events according to importance. We can embed target vocabulary in the activity, and put these target words in bold or underline them. The following activity practices quantity words in English, particularly different kinds of containers. In my experience, firstly, I had to write own ranking by myself, and had opportunity to discuss the rankings with my friends in order to know their opinion.

Activity 4. Vocabulary ladder puzzle.

In this task, you can construct a ladder of five words that all have the same number of letters. For example: cat, cut, cup, pup, pop. These five words are the answers for this word ladder puzzle. To create the puzzle, I replaced all of the letters with dashes to indicate how many letters are in each word. .

e.g.: _____ My first pet was a ____.

_____ When I was shaving this morning, I ____ myself.

In doing this activity, I discovered that learner of new vocabulary frequently talk about a word several times, thus producing multiple encounters with the word.

English language learners need to increase their vocabulary knowledge. As I mentioned above, such activities will help learners focus their attention on key vocabulary, require learners to retrieve the forms and meanings of the new words, and encourage learners to identify and develop a personalized inventory of strategies for vocabulary learning. Our ultimate goal is to be active vocabulary learners and achieve our goals.

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